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Benedicamus Domino tropes in the Birgittine Order: embellishing everyday liturgy

ONE of the main characteristic features of the Birgittine sisters' Office liturgy, the *Cantus sororum*, is to this day its monophonic character.¹ Polyphony was never at any point a means of embellishing the Office or Mass chants. Both polyphony and organs were strictly forbidden by St Birgitta, the Order's founder, who emphasized humility in every way.² Instead of polyphony, troping was the principal technique for embellishment in the Birgittine liturgy. The Birgittines, in other words, ornamented their liturgy by using verbal commentary rather than musical textures. Tropes are found, for example, in the ferial singing of the Gloria and Agnus Dei at Mass. Troping was not restricted to special feast-days but was a way of embellishing the daily liturgy. The content of the tropes was always Mariocentric, mirroring the Order's focus on devotion to the Virgin Mary. In general monastic practice, tropes were not cultivated much after the Middle Ages, but the Birgittines continued to sing them until the late 19th century.³

The only chant genre in the *Cantus sororum* that is consistently troped is the *Benedicamus Domino*, which concluded Lauds and Vespers. Each weekday in the sisters' Office liturgy had one troped version for the *Benedicamus Domino*, thus seven in total. The originally short concluding versicles of the *Benedicamus* were, in Birgittine hands, developed into lengthier chants. The purpose of the tropes was simple and consistent: to enhance the Marian character of the Birgittine sisters' liturgy. For the Little Hours, untroped *Benedicamus* chants were used. These will not be treated here and I only briefly address the cycle of *Benedicamus Domino* with Proper tropes and added Alleluias

that were sung during the Easter season.⁴ The Easter tropes partly overlap with the *Benedicamus* tropes for regular daily use, but some differ from the ones discussed below, a fact that merits future examination.⁵

In general, Birgittine *Benedicamus Domino* tropes remain largely unstudied, with the exception of a 1977 Master's thesis by Viveca Servatius.⁶ Although she only discusses *Benedicamus Domino* tropes for Saturday and Sunday, these English versions of the *Benedicamus* tropes are entirely consistent with the sources I investigate here, and this is characteristic of the homogeneity of liturgical practice across various Birgittine abbeys.

***Cantus sororum*: a short overview**

The Birgittine Order was founded by St Birgitta of Sweden (c.1303–1373) and opened its first abbey in Vadstena in south-east Sweden in 1384. St Birgitta was a mystic already famous during her lifetime for revelations that reached a wide contemporary audience. Her revelations included the Rule for the Order, which gave this Rule divine status.⁷ According to the Rule, the Birgittine Order was founded by Christ in honour of his mother the Virgin Mary and was intended principally for women, though it did also include men.⁸ The sisters' Office, the *Cantus sororum*, is a repertory consisting of some 200 chants that was created exclusively for use in the Birgittine Order. It is the only liturgical repertory known to have been compiled to be performed only by women, and is constructed as a weekly cycle in the form of a ferial Office with one Office per day devoted to the Virgin Mary and her role in salvation.

The content of each day in the *Cantus sororum* may be summarized as follows:

SUNDAY: Creation, joy in the triune God. Mary as the ideal model for creation.

MONDAY: Beauty and fall of the angels. Mary venerated by the angels.

TUESDAY: Fall of Adam, the Patriarchs. Mary as premediated protector of the fallen.

WEDNESDAY: Birth of Mary and childhood. The Conception.

THURSDAY: Incarnation of the Word. The Annunciation.

FRIDAY: Suffering and death of Christ. Mary's suffering.

SATURDAY: Virgin's faith in Christ. Mary's death and Assumption.⁹

The *Cantus sororum* is a mix of borrowings of chants and texts from the standard repertory of plainchant, chants unique to the Birgittines without external concordances (*unica*), and reworkings of borrowed material. This Office was always the same, regardless of diocese, and it changed very little during the liturgical year. In contrast to the sisters, the Birgittine brothers had no liturgy specifically created for them. In accordance with the Rule, they adopted the liturgy in use in the diocese in which the abbey was situated.¹⁰ The brothers' role was to offer in-house assistance by celebrating Mass and hearing confessions. They were also, in contrast to the sisters (including the abbess), allowed to travel outside the abbey. Spiritually, they complemented the sisters' consistently Marian-focused devotion with a liturgy that to a greater extent observed the liturgical year. Together these two liturgies created a so-called 'greater liturgy' which was never the same in any two abbeys. Sisters and brothers not only formed a spiritual unit but also an administrative one, a 'double abbey', where the sisters and brothers inhabited the same cloistered area, though were separate within it.¹¹ The groups also had separate spaces in the abbey church when celebrating their liturgies; these were said in succession, with the brothers' Office said first, followed by the sisters'. A solemn character always characterized the liturgy of the Birgittine sisters: according to their customary, the sisters' liturgy is always festal, and because of this they could incorporate elements into their daily liturgy that were normally reserved for solemnities.¹²

This explains the unusual troping of ferial items—such as the *Benedicamus Domino* versicle—and also the daily singing of a sequence, a Mass chant normally restricted for higher feast-days.¹³

The Birgittine weekly *Benedicamus Domino* tropes

This article offers a new examination of ferial *Benedicamus Domino* tropes, based on sources from the Birgittine abbeys of Vadstena (Sweden), Mariënwater (the Netherlands), Maria Refugie (the Netherlands), Altomünster (Germany) and Mariëntroon (Belgium). The *Benedicamus Domino* tropes are, as noted above and like the rest of the *Cantus sororum*, a very stable repertory among Birgittine abbeys. The chosen source for the melodies transcribed here is not from the mother house, Vadstena, but rather from Altomünster, because the preserved Vadstena sources contain liturgical formulas and chant melodies that are less complete than in sources from daughter houses. This disparity is probably because Vadstena Abbey, as the mother foundation, upheld a much stronger oral tradition than its daughter foundations, which consequently needed to fix their liturgy in writing to a greater extent. In order to reconstruct the sisters' liturgy in Vadstena, therefore, sources from this abbey need to be supplemented by those from the daughter houses.

The *Benedicamus Domino* tropes in the Vadstena sources are found in so-called 'directoria chori', which—in this context—are collections of music and text incipits that remind the sisters of the beginning of each individual chant, omitting the rest of the melodies and texts, which they already knew by rote. This is a type of book unique to Vadstena among the Birgittine abbeys. In the *Benedicamus Domino* tropes, however, the *Benedicamus* section with its Proper trope is fully notated.¹⁴ The respond, 'Deo gratias', is omitted, but as was common practice, this respond was probably closely based on the *Benedicamus* melody.¹⁵ The *Benedicamus* versicle was performed by two sisters, as stated in their customary, the *Lucidarium*.¹⁶

In order to avoid a reconstruction that conflates manuscript versions, I present melodies from a source where *Benedicamus Domino* tropes and their 'Deo gratias' responds are written out in their

entirety. This is the 1495 antiphoner-gradual from Altomünster (D-FS, Hss Alto Ms. P An 4), probably written in the Birgittine abbey Maria Mai, which was founded at Altomünster in 1488 and to which this antiphoner-gradual was later transferred.¹⁷ The book contains a complete *Cantus sororum* cycle, including all sung items and a gradual section with the sisters' Masses: a set of Marian Masses for use throughout the year with *Salve sancta parens* as ferial Mass. The antiphoner-gradual is a typical Birgittine book-type, also preserved in daughter houses in Mariënwater and Mariëntroon, but no example survives from Vadstena.

Texts and melodies

The texts and melodies for the Birgittine *Benedicamus Domino* tropes reflect the general compilation of the *Cantus sororum*: a mix of unique pieces, straightforward borrowings and reworkings of borrowed material. Earlier scholarship has sought to trace the *Cantus sororum* back to its founder St Birgitta, and especially to her collaborator and confessor magister, Petrus Olavi from Skänninge. In Birgitta's revelations, magister Petrus is named as the originator of the *Cantus sororum*, and whilst we know that he played an important role in the working out of the Birgittine Order, it is unlikely that he was the sole creator of this liturgy. No notated sources of the Birgittine liturgy are preserved from earlier than the middle of the 15th century, and consequently Birgitta's and Petrus's inputs are difficult to determine. However, it seems that the Birgittine liturgy—in the form we know it from the comparatively late notated sources that survive—was initiated by magister Petrus and completed by the Birgittines in Vadstena in a process beginning in 1370, when the Order obtained papal approbation. The work was eventually finished in the 1420s, such that the liturgy was codified and ready to be used when the abbey church was dedicated in 1430.¹⁸ There is no reason to doubt that the Birgittine sisters themselves were involved in this work, and two facts speak in favour of their involvement. First, the sheer number of sisters was far greater than that of the brothers; an ideal Birgittine abbey housed 60 sisters and 13 brothers. Second, the sisters were not occupied by the duties which took

up a considerable amount of brothers' time, such as hearing confessions, preparing and performing sermons and travelling. To this can be added an increasing awareness, thanks to recent scholarship, of sisters' agency in shaping their own monastic liturgies.¹⁹ Since, as demonstrated by other articles in this issue, the *Benedicamus Domino* repertory seems to have been especially important in female communities, the idea that the sisters themselves were active in creating their own *Benedicamus* tropes is plausible.

I now examine each ferial trope in turn, with a concluding discussion of the entire corpus.²⁰

1. Sunday

BENEDICAMUS virginis filio cum patre et flamine sacro
vero deo et DOMINO. DEO DICAMUS GRACIAS.

Let us bless the Lord for the birth of his mother, for the son of the eternal king of heaven and earth and hell. Let us give thanks to God.²¹

This *Benedicamus Domino* trope has no known concordances outside the Birgittine Order. The melody consists of two parts in an Aa form (see [ex.1](#)). The strong cadential points on 'flamine sacro' and 'et Domino', respectively, mark the twofold structure.²² The modal designation offers different possibilities. The chant opens and closes on C, with the range extending a 3rd above (E) and a 4th below (G). The use of C as a final was not unusual for the Birgittine *Benedicamus Domino* tropes, as will be shown below. Within the modal system, this could be viewed as a transposed form of mode 8, or even as an untransposed form of a mode 8 that opens and closes on the tenor pitch (C) rather than the final (G). This use of a scale resembling C major is—as shown below—not uncommon for Birgittine *Benedicamus Domino* settings. Servatius calls this transposed mode 8 pure major tonality ('ren dur').²³ However, the range points more to mode 7, which is why another alternative is to analyse it as G mode mixing features of modes 7 and 8. I will return to the question of modal designation later. Barclay argues that many unidentified *Benedicamus Domino* use standard motifs or stock phrases from the second and eighth modes.²⁴ However, no such motifs or stock phrases can be identified in this chant.

Be - ne - di - ca - mus vir - gi - nis fi - li - o cum pat - re

et fla - mi - ne sac - ro

ve - ro De - o et Do - mi - no.

De - o di - ca - mus gra - ci - as.

2. Monday

BENEDICAMUS superni regis unigenito quem benedicat angelorum infinita concio. O virgo Maria quem genuisti nos commenda DOMINO. DEO DICAMUS GRACIAS.

Let us bless the only begotten of the highest king, whom an infinite assembly of angels blesses. O virgin Mary, who gave birth to him, commend us to the Lord. Let us give thanks to God.

Monday's *Benedicamus Domino* trope is based on the *Clementiam* melisma, one of the most widely transmitted *Benedicamus Domino* melodies in the Middle Ages, originally borrowed from a responsory for St Nicholas.²⁵ There is no obvious thematic link between the melody and the Birgittines; rather, it shows how common the use of the *Clementiam* melisma was in many liturgical contexts. The melody is, as is common in melismas borrowed for *Benedicamus* chants, in AAB form (see ex.2).²⁶ Like the Sunday *Benedicamus Domino*, this chant has a strong focus on C and again defies clear modal designation. What is puzzling is that the chant begins on D but ends on C, which makes the transition from C at the close of 'Domino' to the D opening 'Deo dicamus' problematic, since it does not correspond to the previous phrase in an organic way. Is this chant a mix of D and C modes? That the *Clementiam* melisma does not have the initial D but omits this pitch and starts on G indicates that the starting D was added

later (perhaps as a unique Birgittine contribution, since this starting D is consistently found in Birgittine sources for this chant).²⁷ This chant can therefore best be described as another Birgittine *Benedicamus Domino* using a scale resembling C major.²⁸

3. Tuesday

BENEDICAMUS quem nobis ora prophetica nasci spondebant ex matre criminis nescia DOMINO. DEO DICAMUS GRACIAS.

Let us bless the Lord, the one whom prophetic mouths promised to be born from a mother unaware of sin. Let us give thanks to God.

This *Benedicamus Domino* trope is also set to a melody resembling the C scale, giving it the character of a major tonality or a transposed G mode. The melody has an AA form consisting of two falling octaves and a concluding 'coda' on 'Domino' (see ex.3). The chant is related to the Sanctus trope *Clangat hodie*, a trope discussed by Charles Atkinson.²⁹ The general use of the C scale, common to all three examples discussed so far, should not be seen as a late medieval move towards what later would become major/minor tonality. Atkinson remarks that the C scale was treated in the 9th-century treatises *Scolica enchiriadis* and *De harmonica institutione*, where it is specifically identified with instruments.³⁰ The Birgittine text, though, bears no traces of connections to instruments, and in any case, as pointed out

This melody is, in contrast to the previous ones, a unique Birgittine chant with an interesting melodic association. It is related to the Birgittine Magnificat antiphon for Saturday Vespers *Maria, Maria* by a shared opening (marked with boxes in ex.4 and 5), although this particular phrase is not unique to the Birgittines, a variant is found in the gradual responsory *Felix namque*. The responsory was commonly used at the feast of the Purification, and the Birgittines also used it for other Marian feasts (see ex.6). While the responsory motif is not identical, it shares much of the same melodic outline. The phrase with this motif does not open the responsory (as the version in the Magnificat antiphon does) but is found in the middle of the chant at the text ‘*Maria*’. I propose that the responsory motif was borrowed, reworked and adopted into the new Birgittine chant repertory and used as a basis for both the Magnificat antiphon and the *Benedicamus Domino* trope. Borrowing a phrase with the text ‘*Maria*’ is an example of how carefully the Birgittines aimed to charge their Mariocentric liturgy with Marian associations. Using a phrase

from a chant for a Marian feast as the basis of new material in the Birgittine sisters’ Office was a way of underlining and deepening their devotion to the Virgin.³² This *Benedicamus* trope has, in contrast to the previous ones, no easily definable repetitive form, although cadence points are discernible at ‘*matris*’ and ‘*filio*’. The Easter trope for Wednesday has the same melody and text until ‘*regis filio*’, when it is followed by three Alleluias.³³

5. Thursday

BENEDICAMUS devotis mentibus sugenti humillime puellule virgineas mamillas immense DOMINO. DEO DICAMUS GRACIAS.

Let us bless the Lord with great humility the devout minds nursing at the virgin girl’s breasts. Let us give thanks to God.

This chant has no known melodic concordances, but the opening words, ‘*Benedicamus devotis mentibus*’, are typically used as the opening of a *Benedicamus* trope text which accompanies

Ex.4 Saturday Magnificat antiphon *Maria, Maria* in the *Cantus sororum* from D-FS: Hss Alto Ms. p An 4, fol.72r

Ma - ri - a, Ma - ri - a, to - ci - us
sanc - ti - ta - tis tu
prin - ci - pa - lis gem - ma, nos ti - bi hu - mi - li - ter
da ser - vi - re, et ab hos - tis an - ti - qui mil - le
mil - len - is frau - di - bus con - ser - va, Ma - ri - a.
Magnificat

Ex.5 *Benedicamus Domino* trope *pro nativitate* for Wednesday in the *Cantus sororum* from D-FS: Hss Alto Ms. P An 4, fol.76r

Be - ne - di - ca - mus pro na - ti - vi - ta - te su - e
 mat - ris e - ter - ni re - gis
 fi - li - o, ce - li ter - re - que
 ac in - fer - no - rum Do - mi - no.
 De - o di - ca - mus gra - ci - as.

the *Clementiam* melody, the melody used (with a different text) for the *Benedicamus* trope in the Birgittine’s Monday liturgy. This means that the Birgittine *Benedicamus Domino* tropes for Monday and Thursday are connected through the *Clementiam* melisma: one uses its melody, and the other adopts the typical opening of its trope text. It is hard to explain why the melody and text associated with the *Clementiam* melisma were disassociated in the Birgittine liturgy, and there is no obvious thematical connection between Monday and Thursday in the *Cantus sororum*, apart from its ever-present Marian themes. Nevertheless, it demonstrates a certain creativity on the part of the creators of the Birgittine liturgy: they knew a trope text associated with the *Clementiam* melisma but chose to craft their own text instead, and they decided to adopt a common textual opening for a *Benedicamus* trope to accompany their own newly created melody. This melody is in mode 1, with D and A as the expected structural pitches, though it

ends on A, rather than D. The form is AB where the B section begins at ‘puellule’ (see ex.7).³⁴

6. Friday

BENEDICAMUS innocenti virginis filio pro reis morti tradito perhenniter viventi DOMINO. DEO DICAMUS revincenti nos a fauce tartari ad aulam celi reducenti infinitas GRACIAS.

Let us bless the Lord the son of the innocent virgin, handed over to death, living forever. Let us give infinite thanks to God, who recovered us from the throat of Tartarus, who will lead us back to the hall of heaven.

Friday’s *Benedicamus Domino* trope—in mode 4 and in AB form—is also without known concordances (see ex.8). According to Barclay’s listing, mode 4 is a very small category for *Benedicamus Domino* melodies, and none of them resemble the Birgittine’s Friday trope.³⁵ This trope has a slightly more syllabic structure than the other ferial Birgittine *Benedicamus Domino* tropes, and the

Ex.6 Offertory *Felix namque* for Purificatio Mariae from D-FS: Hss Alto Ms. P An 4, fol.106v

Fe - lix nam - que

sac - ra vir - go Ma - ri - a

et om - ni lau - de

dig - nis - si - ma qui - a ex te

or - tus est sol ius - ti - ci - e Chris - tus de - us

nos - ter al - le - lu - ia.

melody's more restricted character is fitting for a day commemorating Good Friday. Yet in stark contrast to the restrained character, the troped *Deo dicamus gratias* stands out. This is the only instance of a troped *Deo dicamus gratias* in the *Cantus sororum* and is only found in sources outside Vadstena Abbey, since the Vadstena sources do not—as noted above—include the *Deo gratias* responds. Did this trope emerge outside Vadstena, demonstrating that the Birgittine liturgy was not static once it had left its mother house? Or was it also in oral circulation in Vadstena, eventually written down only in copies for the daughter houses? These questions remain open, but

the reason for extending the *Benedicamus* trope with an additionally troped *Deo dicamus gratias* on Fridays—while simultaneously maintaining a solemn simplicity in the syllabic *Benedicamus* section—is probably because of the importance of Fridays to the Birgittine Order. Each Friday liturgy was extended with processions, and on this day the longest chant in the entire *Cantus sororum* is sung: the great responsory for Matins *Palluerunt pie matris*, which is a depiction of the Virgin Mary at the cross. Once again we see the Birgittine strategy of highlighting a solemn day by using both simplicity and length rather than polyphonic texture.

Ex.7 *Benedicamus Domino* trope *devotis mentibus* for Thursday in the *Cantus sororum* from D-FS: Hss Alto Ms. p An 4, fol.76r

Be - ne - di - ca - mus de - vo - tis men - ti - bus su - gen - ti hu - mil - li - me
 pu - el - lu - le vir - gi - ne - as ma - mil - las, im - men - so
 Do - mi - no.
 De - o di - ca - mus gra - ci - as.

Ex.8 *Benedicamus Domino* trope *innocenti virginis* for Friday in the *Cantus sororum* from D-FS: Hss Alto Ms. p An 4, fol.76v

Be - ne - di - ca - mus in - no - cen - ti vir - gi - nis fi - li - o,
 pro re - is mor - ti tra - di - to, per - hen - ni - ter vi - ven - ti Do - mi - no.
 De - o di - ca - mus re - vin - cen - ti nos a fau - ce tar - ta - ri, ad au - lam ce - li
 re - du - cen - ti, in - fi - ni - tas gra - ci - as.

7. Saturday

BENEDICAMUS in laudem patris qui matrem suam Mariam benedixit in eternum DOMINO. DEO DICAMUS GRACIAS.

Let us bless the Lord in praise of the Father who has blessed his mother Mary for eternity. Let us give thanks to God.

The last *Benedicamus domino* trope employs another of the most widespread *Benedicamus* melodies of the Middle Ages: the *Flos filius* melisma from the Marian Matins responsory *Stirps Jesse* (see [ex.9](#)). This responsory is commonly used for Marian feasts at Lauds and Vespers, and Anne Walters Robertson traces the use of this melisma as

Ex.9 *Benedicamus Domino* trope in laudem patris for Saturday in the *Cantus sororum* from D-FS: Hss Alto Ms. p An 4, fol.77r

Be - ne - di - ca - mus in lau - dem pat - ris, qui mat - rem su - am Ma - ri - am
be - ne - dix - it in e - ter - num, Do - mi - no.
De - o di - ca - mus gra - ti - as.

Benedicamus at Vespers and Lauds on high feasts back to Cluny and at least to the 11th century.³⁶ It is found in Scandinavian sources, such as the *Liber Scole Virginis* from Lund Cathedral.³⁷

The Marian connection to *Stirps Jesse* is interesting for obvious reasons, as this responsory is sung in the *Cantus sororum* not on Saturdays, but as the second Matins responsory for Wednesdays, when the Birgittine sisters celebrated the birth of the Virgin Mary. This creates a thematic link between the days in the *Cantus sororum* in a more obvious way than the use of the *Benedicamus* melody that borrows the *Clementiam* melisma or the Sanctus trope *Clangat hodie*. Saturday commemorates the Virgin Mary's death and ascension. In other words, Wednesday and Saturday frame the life of the Virgin Mary from birth to death. The use of a pre-existing melody that is also associated in the *Cantus sororum* with Mary's nativity is another example of the way in which texts and music create links across and between the items and themes of the *Cantus sororum*, binding the Office together as a unified and self-referential entity.

Conclusion

This study of seven *Benedicamus Domino* tropes from the *Cantus sororum* offers a glimpse into the rich universe of this liturgical repertory. Though comprising only a small percentage of the chants in this much bigger corpus, the ferial *Benedicamus*

tropes demonstrate and encapsulate features that are typical of the chants of the Birgittine sisters more generally. The Birgittines borrowed from known *Benedicamus Domino* models outside the Order but also made their own contributions. Thematically the chants relate, as expected, to the themes of their Proper day in the *Cantus sororum*. Musically these chants are a mix of borrowings, reworkings and unique contributions, showing a diversity of form and modality where the dominance of melodies centred around C stands out. Sometimes, modal designation is difficult to determine. Friday—a day of key importance in the Birgittine liturgy—is notable for its inclusion of an extended troped *Deo dicamus gratias* response to the *Benedicamus Domino* versicle. The Wednesday and Saturday *Benedicamus Domino* tropes reference and connect to other items in the Birgittine Office liturgy in their use of appropriate allusions to, and borrowings of, other Marian chants. Wednesday opens with a quotation from the gradual responsory for the feast of the Purification *Felix namque es* (also used as the opening of the Magnificat responsory, *Maria, Maria*) and thus links to the Birgittine Mass liturgy. Saturday borrows the *Benedicamus* melody from the Marian Matins responsory *Stirps Jesse*. The Monday and Thursday tropes each adopt different aspects of the same well-known *Benedicamus* trope: Monday makes a new text for the famous

melody, while Thursday opens with a standard and widespread trope text set to a new and unique Birgittine chant.

In sum, these seven *Benedicamus Domino* tropes show the numerous strategies that were at work in creating the *Cantus sororum*, underlining how carefully worked out and creative the Birgittine sisters' liturgy was. The unique chants in the Birgittine repertory, and here in particular the ferial *Benedicamus*

Domino tropes, are just one facet of the sisters' activities in Vadstena. It is certain that the Birgittine sisters had the skills to copy texts and music, that they illuminated books and embroidered.³⁸ In this context, it is likely that the sisters themselves actively shaped the music and texts of their own liturgy, creating tropes for daily use that served to enhance and embellish their liturgy, in their devotion to the Virgin Mary.

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¹ Since the 1970s, the *Cantus sororum* has been sung in the vernacular in the remaining abbeys (Swedish, Dutch and, until 2011, English in Syon Abbey). The vernacular *Cantus sororum* is treated in K. Strinnholm Lagergren, 'Ordet blev sång: Liturgisk musik i katolska kloster 2005–2007' (PhD diss., Gothenburg University/Skellefteå, 2009) and Lagergren, *Birgittine chantsapes*, forthcoming.

² See 'Extravagant revelations' (an addition to the Birgittine Rule), chapter 17 in *The revelations of St. Birgitta of Sweden, vol.4: The heavenly emperor's book to kings, The rule and minor works*, ed. B. Morris and D. Searby (Oxford, 2015), p.241.

³ This is also the case with their extensive sequence repertory, which continued to be practised into the 20th century. See K. Strinnholm Lagergren, 'The Birgittine Mass

liturgy through five centuries: a case study of the Uden sources', *Archiv für Liturgiewissenschaft*, lvii (2015), pp.49–71.

⁴ These are included in V. Servatius, 'Benedicamustroperna i *Cantus sororum*' (Master's thesis, Stockholm University, 1977).

⁵ A list of these chants is found in Servatius, 'Benedicamustroperna', p.19.

⁶ Servatius, 'Benedicamustroperna', p.19. Anne Bagnall Yardley addresses them briefly using sources from Syon Abbey in England, founded in 1415; see A. B. Yardley, 'The Bridgettine nuns of Syon Abbey', in *Performing piety: musical culture in medieval English nunneries*, ed. A. B. Yardley (New York, 2006), pp.222–3.

⁷ The Birgittine Rule is an addition to the Augustinian Rule, since the establishment of new monastic rules was not allowed in Birgitta's time.

⁸ Some scholars prefer the term 'female abbey with male assistance', because the Order was founded first and foremost for women. See *The revelations of St. Birgitta*, pp.125–6.

⁹ After M. Urberg, 'Music in devotional lives of the Birgittine brothers and sisters at Vadstena Abbey (c.1373–1545)' (PhD diss., University of Chicago, 2016), p.28.

¹⁰ *The revelations of St. Birgitta*, pp.241–2.

¹¹ Since the liturgy of the sisters and brothers functioned as one unit, I prefer the term 'double abbey'. Tore Nyberg discusses the role and function of the Birgittine brothers in T. Nyberg, *Birgittinsk festgåva: Studier om den heliga Birgitta och Birgittinorden* (Uppsala, 1991), pp.111–30.

¹² *Heliga Birgittas Uppenbarelser Bd 5 Bihang*, ed. G. Klemming (Stockholm, 1883–4), pp.68–9.

¹³ The sequence repertory is discussed in Strinnholm Lagergren, 'The Birgittine Mass liturgy', pp.49–71.

¹⁴ This is also noted in Servatius, 'Benedicamustroperna', p.18.

¹⁵ A. W. Robertson, "'Benedicamus Domino': the unwritten tradition", *Journal of the American Musicological Society*, xli (1988), pp.1–62, at p.32.

¹⁶ *Heliga Birgittas Uppenbarelser*, p.59.

¹⁷ Antiphoner-gradual from Altomünster Birgittine Abbey: D-FS: Hss Alto Ms. P An 4 from 1495. Inventory: <http://birgittine.org/source/70974> (accessed 7 January 2022). Digital images: <https://www.digitale-sammlungen.de/en/view/bsb00110090?page=1> (accessed 7 January 2022).

¹⁸ This is an argument explored at length in Lagergren, *Birgittine chantscapes*, forthcoming.

¹⁹ See, for example, J. F. Hamburger, *Liturgical life and Latin learning at Paradies bei Soest, 1300–1425: inscription and illumination in the choir books of a north German Dominican convent* (Münster, 2016) for an example of Dominican nuns creating sequences.

²⁰ Transcriptions are in modern notation using a treble clef to facilitate possible performances of these unique tropes. Original spellings are retained. The source is very carefully written, such that there are no grammatical or notational errors that require correction. Since these chants were performed by women no transposition of the treble clef was necessary.

²¹ Translations into English of all tropes were made by Dr Robert Andrews.

²² The Easter version for Sunday uses only the A part with the same text, replacing the a part with three Alleluias.

²³ For example, Servatius, ‘Benedicamustroperna’, p.44.

²⁴ B. M. Barclay, ‘The medieval repertory of polyphonic untroped Benedicamus Domino settings’ (PhD diss., University of California

at Los Angeles, 1977), p.52. Barclay’s collection of *Benedicamus Domino* melodies ordered by mode is found on pp.53–91.

²⁵ Discussed at several places in Robertson, “Benedicamus Domino”, the melody is found on p.22, music example 12.

²⁶ Robertson, “Benedicamus Domino”, p.53.

²⁷ Ten concordances of this chant are listed in the database <http://birgittine.org>.

²⁸ The Easter trope for Monday employs the same melody but a different text.

²⁹ C. M. Atkinson, ‘The Ordinary chants of the Roman Mass, with their tropes: the odyssey of an edition’, in *Ars Edendi. Lecture Series. Volume IV*, ed. B. Crostini, G. Iversen and B. Møller Jensen (Stockholm, 2016), pp.50–84.

³⁰ Atkinson, ‘The Ordinary chants of the Roman Mass’, pp.73–4.

³¹ The Easter trope for Tuesday employs the same melody but a different text.

³² The antiphon *Maria, Maria* and its many reworkings in the Birgittine liturgy, as well as the problem of modal designation of this piece, is discussed at length in Lagergren, *Birgittine chantscapes*, forthcoming.

³³ In the Easter version of the trope, ‘nativitate’ can be replaced with ‘conceptione’, ‘presentatione’ or ‘nativitate’, showing that this trope could be adapted for different Marian feasts.

³⁴ The Easter trope is loosely related to this ferial trope, sharing only its *Benedicamus* opening and ending on D, the *finalis* of the first mode.

³⁵ Barclay, ‘The medieval repertory’, pp.72–3.

³⁶ Robertson, “Benedicamus Domino”, p.11. See Barclay, ‘The medieval repertory’, p.32, for a list of sources.

³⁷ For example, *Liber scole virginis en medeltida samling av Mariamusik i Lund: faksimilutgåva av LUB MH 14 med inledning, transkription och kommentar/ A medieval collection of Marian music in Lund: facsimile edition of LUB MH 14 with introduction, transcription and commentary*, ed. F. Bohlin (Lund, 2003), p.87.

³⁸ E. Lindqvist Sandgren, *Birgittinerna och deras bilder: En studie av bild, rum och betraktare i Vadstena klosterkyrka omkring år 1500* (Uppsala, 2021) <https://www.kriterium.se/site/books/m/10,51509/kriterium.29/>; and I. Hedström, ‘Medeltidens svenska bönböcker: kvinnligt skriftbruk i Vadstena kloster’ (PhD diss., University of Oslo, 2009).

Karin Lagergren

***Benedicamus Domino* tropes in the Birgittine Order: embellishing everyday liturgy**

A remarkable feature of the Birgittine monastic Order is its daily use of tropes for the embellishment of an exclusively monophonic liturgy. Ferial tropes were sung in both Mass and Office and their purpose was to highlight the Marian devotion that was central to the Order's spirituality. In the Birgittine sisters' ferial Office liturgy, the so-called *Cantus sororum*, the *Benedicamus Domino* was a notable location for

the provision of tropes, which were performed daily at Lauds and Vespers. These *Benedicamus* tropes are a complex mix of *unica*, as well as musical and textual patchworks of pre-existing and new and/or remodelled musical and textual material. This article explains the place and importance of *Benedicamus Domino* tropes in Birgittine liturgy and spirituality, illustrated by new transcriptions of the *Benedicamus* tropes that were consistently assigned to embellish each particular day of the week.

Keywords: Birgittine liturgy; *Cantus sororum*; plainchant; Office liturgy; tropes; *Benedicamus Domino*; modal analysis; Birgittine Order; St Birgitta of Sweden; nuns; female religious